

OSCAR Learning and Mentoring Exploitation Plan

This document is licensed under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

<http://oscar-ai.eu/>

Authors

Szidónia Rusu,

Project Manager, SciLink Foundation

Dr. Emese Vita,

Project Manager, SciLink Foundation

Dr. Gábor Kismihók

Head of Learning and Skill Analytics, TIB

Dr. Francisco Valente Gonçalves,

Research & Innovation Director at RUMO, Senior Clinical Psychologist

Inês Gaspar, MSc

Researcher and Senior Clinical Psychologist at RUMO

Mathias Schroijen

Project Manager, Université Libre de Bruxelles, Eurodoc

Adam Keszler,

Managing Director, SciLink Foundation

Table of Contents

Project summary and main objectives	4
About the Project	4
Project partners	4
Dissemination channels and branding materials	5
Dissemination channels	5
Branding materials	5
Web-based channels:	5
Exploitation Planning Strategy and Outcomes	6
Background analysis (PEST)	6
Swot analysis of eDoer platform	8
Target Audience	9
Competition Analysis – best content curation platforms	11
Sustainability of the results after the end of the OSCAR Project	13
Impact and indicators of exploitation and sustainability	16
Short term impacts	16
Long term impacts	18

Project summary and main objectives

About the Project

Project title: OSCAR, the “**O**nline, open learning recommendations and mentoring towards Sustainable research **CAR**eers”

Funding: Erasmus+ Key Action 204 Higher Education

Duration: September 2020-August 2023

Budget: 427 818 €

The principal objective of OSCAR E+ Strategic Partnership was to develop, deploy and validate a personalized AI based learning, training and online mentoring service for researchers in order to support researchers, research master students and doctoral training participants in their career management and mental health awareness skills development. Therefore, the OSCAR project focused on the development of an online, AI driven open learning recommendation framework focusing on mental health and career management.

Project partners

Coordinator

TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology and University Library, Germany

Partners

USI - University of Siegen, Germany

CALP – Career & Life Planning, Ireland

RUMO, Portugal

Marie Curie Alumni Association, Belgium

SciLink Foundation, Netherlands

Associated Partner

Eurodoc – The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, Belgium

This document is licensed under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

<http://oscar-ai.eu/>

Dissemination channels and branding materials

Dissemination channels

1. **Recommender prototype:**

<http://edoer.eu/>

2. **About the OSCAR Project:**

<https://projects.tib.eu/oscar-ai/about-the-project/>

3. **Social media:**

https://twitter.com/edoer_info

Branding materials

Branding materials will include the following:

Graphic identity: OSCAR, eDoer and Erasmus+ logos

Web-based channels:

1. **Learner view**

<https://www.learn.edoer.eu>

2. **Content curator view**

<https://www.cc.edoer.eu>

3. **Organisational view**

<https://learn.edoer.eu/organizations/oscar/contents>

This document is licensed under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

<http://oscar-ai.eu/>

Exploitation Planning Strategy and Outcomes

In order to achieve an efficient strategic planning regarding the exploitation of the OSCAR project after its end, we used several tools to assess the external macro-environmental factors that could impact the eDoer and the OSCAR methodology. We made a brief analysis on political, economic, social and technological factors in order to understand the broader context in which OSCAR operates. We also made a SWOT analysis of the OSCAR project in order to assess its internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats. In order to understand the market landscape the competitor analysis helps to gain a clear understanding of the overall market dynamics including the top content curator applications and platforms.

Background analysis (PEST)

1. Political factor:

- Policies related to data privacy, security and intellectual property rights
- EU initiatives and funding programs supporting digital innovation

2. Economic factor:

- Potential for growth in the education and technology sectors, R+D sectors
- Funding opportunities on international and local levels
- Impact of exchange rate fluctuation on costs, pricing and profitability

3. Technological factor:

- AI Advancements> how to assess the competitiveness of the platform in terms of AI capabilities, algorithms and machine learning models
- Infrastructure: availability and quality of digital infrastructure and devices within EU countries. Delivering seamless learning experience across different connection speeds and devices
- Data Privacy (GDPR): data collection, storage and processing practices

4. Social factor:

- Adaptation rate to new technological developments, digital literacy and digital divide within the target market
- Willingness among academic institutions, students, educators to embrace and integrate AI-based learning platforms

This document is licensed under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

- Educational trends
- Multicultural diversity: how to adapt the content of the platform to language options, cultural sensitivity and diversity

Based on the PEST analysis the main conclusion and insights can be summarized in various dimensions. The availability of European Union initiatives and funding opportunities supporting digital innovation presents opportunities for further financial support and collaborations in this area. Also there is a potential growth in the education and technology sectors, indicating a favorable market environment for the sustainability and expansion of OSCAR project. According to the latest statistical forecasts, AI will achieve the greatest scientific breakthrough and productivity impact in the coming years in the construction industry, education and health sectors, which may mean the automation of 24-37% of current jobs. (Source: OECD, 2019, AI Summit, 2023). These continuous advancements in AI should be closely monitored to ensure OSCAR remains competitive in terms of AI capabilities, machine learning models and adoption to the target market needs. Overall keeping up with educational trends and accommodating to multicultural diversity and technological innovations, economical growth, will enhance the appeal of the OSCAR project.

Swot analysis of eDoer platform

Strenghts

- Innovative product offering a new approach to AI learning, which is unique in the realm of doctoral education
- Unique value of the content and platform: it is a mixture of human created input and AI interventions
- Content created by experts, not only by a pre-set algorithm
- Transnational approach
- Expert Mentoring

Weaknesses

- Not enough brand recognition
- Lack of public validation of expert input
- Credibility an unique aspect of the content
- Technology dependency> the success of the project mostly relies on the effectiveness of AI-powered recommendations, any technical limitations could affect the quality of the learning experience.

Opportunities

- Integrate a ChatGPT modell
- Add-on expert groups that complement the learning retrieved from the platform
- Constantly refreshing validated contents
- Tailor-made and personalised program and learning materials
- Market demand: the increasing demand for specialized skills and support for early career researchers across various sectors present a significant opportunity for this tool
- Collaboration potential> with organisations, universities, research institutions and industry partners

Threats

- Tough competition in the AI based learning platforms market
- Challenges in reaching the specific target group
- Constantly changing technical environment
- Adoption barriers: overcoming the resistance to change and convince traditional academic institutions to embrace new approaches for career development and mentoring could be challenging.
- Sustainability: Maintaining the quality of AI recommendations and content validation by experts could be an ongoing challenge on the long run.
- Ethical considerations: data privacy, content creation.

Overall the innovative approach and unique content of the OSCAR project are strengths that set it apart in the AI learning platform market, even though it should improve in the sense of brand recognition, public validation of experts and technology dependence. Seizing opportunities through refreshment of the content, collaborations and technology enhancements can drive innovation and growth, as well as recognizing and mitigating the main threats such as high level of market competition or resistance to change. Another conclusion is that sustainability and ethical considerations should be integrated into the long term strategy of the project.

Target Audience

Using a mixed business model, with a focus on the academic environment, the eDoer learning platform reaches multiple target audience as the following:

Specific audience (SA):

1. Academic institutions **B2B**

- eDoer partners with academic institutions to provide the learning platform as a Business-to-Business (B2B) service. This means that universities, colleges and educational institutions can integrate eDoer into their academic programs.

2. Wellbeing departments and Career Offices **B2B**

- eDoer serves as a tailored-made tool for these departments to promote well-being, career readiness and mental health

3. Industry (private companies) **B2B**

- HR/Talent departments
- Health and safety
- Learning and Development

4. Individual users (to everyone except those that are in an emergency situation) **B2C**

- eDoer is accessible to individual users, including professionals, academic students, PhD candidates and young researchers

5. Mental health professionals (that can use eDoer in their practice) **B2B2C**

- mental health professionals can incorporate eDoer into their practice to provide additional resources and support to their clients.

This document is licensed under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

General audience (GA):

All users interested in the learning platform (from different academic backgrounds)

Overall the mixed business model of eDoer primarily focuses on the academic environment by partnering with academic institutions, wellbeing departments and career offices, simultaneously it extends its services to a broader audience, including private companies, mental health professionals and general audience, offering a wide range of resources and support for personal and professional growth, specialized in academic workplace background and environment.

Competition Analysis – best content curation platforms

<i>Nr.</i>	<i>Competitor name/webpage</i>	<i>Specifications and key functions</i>
1	Feedly	Content curation on WordPress website, RSS Aggregator The basic functionality of the plugin is to display information from one site to another: on the one hand displays the information in the feeds on users' site, and on the other hand imports the feeds as posts on the users' website (this is a premium version)
2	Pocket	The application allows users to save an article or a website and to remote servers for later reading. The key functions are the following: the content is always available, even without internet connection, it has a batch save option and works with Evernote, which enables the users to go paper-free and streamline the digital content.
3	BuzzSumo	The application helps the user to discover best engagement content and outreach opportunities across social and search. BuzzSumo is a cloud based app, which helps curate and create content, find influencers and curate their content.
4	SocialPilot	Its used for create, publish and manage and easily customize social media posts across all major platforms, helps the users in social media scheduling and publishing, visualizing content strategies with calendar view.
5	Scoop.it	The platform helps the professionals and small businesses to aggregate relevant content on their website, publish it and share on social media. It is possible to share the information collected on the platform, a free user can have up to two thematic media or two online newspapers.
6	Curata	It is an intelligent content curation software, which crowdsources content from various platforms like websites, social media, blogs.

7	Triberr	Is a content curation tool for influencers, bloggers and small businesses, which helps the user to build up an audience through content marketing. Tiberr constantly monitors the web for updated posts, or share-worthy articles.
8	ContentGems	Is a no-code content discovery tool, where the users can view a stream of web content for the Interests they have created, this can also be shared on social media.
9	UpContent	Is an all-in-one AI-powered content curation platform which allows users to discover, curate and captivate content with their audience.
10	Flipboard	An user friendly content curation tool, the curators can create a mini-magazine for their readers.
11	Quuu	Quuu is the only known and top content curation software which suggests content that is reviewed in-house by humans and not pre-set algorithms. Key features: social media monitoring, posts scheduling, customer engagement, auto publishing, content management, multi-user collaborations
12	Pluralsight	Online learning platform Topics related to technology 180 countries Key features: cloud transformation, security skills, upskilling and reskilling in technology, engineer onboarding, training in tech fluency and software delivery.
13	Mindtool-business	Leadership development, customer education, management training Key functions: the toolkit offers and extensive content library of career tools, tips and courses on all essential soft skills for employees and managers , like time management, communication skills, strategy and coaching or coping with stress and burnout.

In the competitor analysis, content curation was an important aspect as a basic operating principle, so those that have such a basic function and are considered the most used platforms were included in the analysis. What they have in common with eDoer is that they provide for the user high-quality personalized content, providing access to training materials and various content. The difference is that the listed apps are mostly used for marketing and social media appearance and branding, and many of their extensions are only available to premium users, while eDoer's content is for learning and skill development, and beside the AI learning machine has also a human input in the contents.

Sustainability of the results after the end of the OSCAR Project

The business model for the OSCAR project is currently under development and requires more testing and clarifications. However, it appears that a hybrid approach combining multiple business models (B2B, B2C etc.) will likely be necessary to effectively address the goals and main objectives of the project. For the sustainability of the project and in order to enhance content quality control and user experience other important aims of the project are the following:

- a. *Implementing content reporting functionality*, which allows users to flag inappropriate or missing content within eDoer platform, enhancing user experience by promoting content quality and appropriateness
- b. *Integrate eDoer with already existing LMSs (Learning Management Systems)* by investigating and identifying the specific APIs required for seamless integration between eDoer and various established LMSs, enabling streamlined access and utilization for users.

Model	Value proposition	Type of monetization
B2B	Provide to other businesses a platform that offers a catalog with contents that these businesses can use and add/manage for their daily tasks	<p>Basic plan free</p> <p>Other plans with fees (TBC):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Option to have GPT • Contents that are freshly new • Complete rates of experts • Rates from users vs (add-on) rates from experts • Add-on expert groups that complement the learning retrieved from the platform (1 session per month) <p>Value must consider the dimension of the organization and use a “scalability pricing model” (i.e. consider a value per potential user of the organization)</p>
B2C	Provide to users a platform that offers a catalog with contents provided by experts	<p>Basic plan free</p> <p>Other plans with fees (TBC):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Option to have GPT • Contents that are freshly new • Complete rates of experts • Rates from users vs (add-on) rates from experts

<p>B2B2C</p>	<p>Provide to other businesses and organizations a platform that offers a catalog with contents that these businesses can use with their clients as well as create their own contents for their practice</p>	<p>Basic plan free</p> <p>Other plans with fees (TBC):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Option to have GPT • Contents that are freshly new • Complete rates of experts • Rates from users vs (add-on) rates from experts • Use the platform for building a tailor-made program edited only by the business (private courses) <p>Value must consider the dimension of the organization and use a “scalability pricing model” (i.e. consider a value per potential user of the organization)</p>
---------------------	--	---

Impact and indicators of exploitation and sustainability

Short term impacts

	Target groups/potential beneficiaries	Quantitative indicators	Qualitative indicators
Increasing involvement of experts	Leaders, academic members, mental health and career development professionals	At least 5 new experts involved in creating content At least 2 new topics and training courses will be prepared	Increasing quality of learning content and methodology and model
Large number of beneficiaries at an open access level	Individual users (everyone except those that are in an emergency situation)	At least 100 new users from different academic backgrounds 80% feedback and rating of the platform content	Appropriateness and easy accessibility of content and platform Extensibility of the beneficiary group
Innovation (human+AI)	Leaders, policy makers, press and media	At least 100-150 academia members trained about AI based eDoer Increasing number of new innovative ideas which could be implemented in eDoer	Adapting content to multicultural and diversity aspects Increasing level of inclusion

Community support and engagement	Leaders, academic members, mental health and career development professionals	At least 500 new followers on social media At least 100 new users Regular media and press coverage	High level of satisfaction with the content
----------------------------------	---	--	---

Long term impacts

	Target groups/potential beneficiaries	Quantitative indicators	Qualitative indicators
Cooperation with universities, academic institutions	Academic institutions, wellbeing departments and career offices, PhD candidate unions and organisations	At least 2 new contracts and projects related to development of AI learning platform Cooperation with 5 EU based universities	New perceptions about the benefits of AI intervention in learning and teaching activities Feedback of participants
Innovation in AI based learning platforms	Individual users and business, academic institutional users	Increasing number of users of eDoer Increasing number of mentorships Increasing number of content creating experts Copyright license	Constantly increasing quality of the eDoer learning platform
Development in academic education	Policy makers, press and media, leaders of institutions and industry	Increasing number of collaborative and contract based research project Increasing number of media, article and conference coverage	Exchange of knowledge, networking activities, long-term partnerships

Integrate the technology in industry and private companies	HR and Talent departments, Leaders of Health and Safety, Learning and Developments Industries	At least two private company partners and collaboration	Quality of exchanges with the business environment
--	---	---	--